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Deliverable D2.10

Report on data collected on small pelagics and environmental forcing on the west coast of Africa

30/03/2022

Executive Summary

Fisheries of small pelagics, namely sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), chub mackerel (*Scomber colias*) and European anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) in Morocco and Mauritania are extremely important from the socio-economic perspective. They account for the largest biomasses landed and contribute to the national economies through employment and exports of canned products, fish meal and fish oil, while also being a major source of protein for national consumption. Stocks of small pelagics in upwelling regions are characterised by strong variability in recruitment and abundance, with environmental drivers playing a key role. Most stock assessment approaches do not take into account environmental variability or interactions between species, in an ecosystem context. Understanding the drivers of fluctuations in the variability of small pelagics would contribute to improved management and conservation. For all the above reasons, the FarFish project is awarding significant efforts towards estimating population trends of small-pelagics provided by stock assessment models to find the link with environmental variables. The work is broken into two tasks i.e. the data collection part (WP2) and the modelling part (WP6). This document reports on the WP2 task, which includes compiling the data input for different models, like life history parameters and time series of catches, landings, effort, indices of abundance, as well as finding the sources to get different environmental variables.

This deliverable reports on the biological and fisheries data compiled for the three key small pelagic species. Time series suitable for modelling were compiled from a number of sources, national and international as well as fisheries dependent and fisheries independent (research surveys). Life history parameters (growth, weight-length relationships) were also compiled from different sources. Catch data time series are available since the 1970s, with reconstructed time series (Sea Around Us project) extending the time series back to 1950. Fishing effort data is available from the early 1990s, with shorter time series of abundance indices available from research surveys, for Morocco. Time series of fishing effort for Mauritania are however lacking.

Together with time series of environmental variables, the data compiled will feed WP6 where new approaches and models will be applied to gain a better understanding of the population dynamics of the three small pelagics and contribute to improving management. WP6 will fit stock assessment models for these data. Resulting estimates will then be contrasted with different environmental variables and links found will contribute to gain a better understanding of the population dynamics for these three small pelagics. Disentangling the environmental effect over the population could also be further used to enhance management practices.

Abbreviations

CCMAR	Centro de Ciências do Mar
CECAF	Fishery Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
COPACE	Comité des Pêches pour l'Atlantique Centre-Est
CPUE	Catch per unit effort
CS	Case Study
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EU	European Union
FAO	Fisheries and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations
INRH	Institut National de Recherche Halieutique
RSW	Refrigerated Sea Water
UCA	Université Cadi Ayyad
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

The north-west African waters from Morocco to Mauritania are known as one of the most productive worldwide ecosystems due to the upwelling occurring along the coast. This upwelling is due to the strong wind regime from the Azores blowing for a long time period, the Canary Current and the Ekman transport pushing the surface water offshore (INRH, 2017). The high primary production, small number of trophic transfers and relatively high ecological efficiency results in very high biomasses of small pelagic species, namely sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*), chub mackerel (*Scomber colias*) and anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*). However, recruitment of small pelagics is highly variable and largely environmentally driven.

Given the importance of the small pelagics to the fisheries and ecosystems of the North-West African countries, a new task was added to FarFish project: to model the population dynamics of key small pelagic in NW Africa, based on time series of abundance, effort, landings and environmental variables. While the modelling part of the task will be carried out within WP6 of the project, the tasks of compiling existing information of small pelagics in the area was allocated to W2. This implies fishery and non-fishery data (e.g. scientific cruises, biology of the relevant species) necessary to advance in the implementation of integrated models. The task also involves the formatting of this information to run the model(s) that will be applied and to incorporate it into the FarFish database.

The architecture for an integrated model is implemented for one or two relevant species with the information gathered in task 1. It is expected to produce a better model, in terms of processing existing information, than what is presently implemented by CECAF. This will create added value from the project for the fishery and its management.

This report represents a description of available fisheries data for the three small pelagic target species (Sardine, Chub mackerel and Anchovy) from the Moroccan and Mauritanian Atlantic coast. For each of these species, information is given on stock structure, fisheries data (catch and fishing effort), abundance indices, biological data and sampling.

2 Moroccan coast

In Morocco, three main types of production units divide the exploitation of small pelagic resources in the four fishing zones of the Moroccan Atlantic EEZ. The small pelagic stocks distinguished by the Working Group (COPACE-FAO): the northern stock (35°45'–32°N), the central stock “A+B zones” (32°N–26°N) and the southern stock “C zone” (26°N– the southern extent of the species distribution) (FAO, 2001).

Figure 1: Moroccan Atlantic coast and the four fishing zones (INRH, 2017)

2.1 Small pelagic stock structure

The small pelagic fisheries occupy an important place in the Moroccan fisheries sector (FAO, 2001). Table 1 shows the main small pelagic species captured in the north-west African countries (Morocco and Mauritania). However, these upwelling ecosystems are very dynamic and show strong variability on all spatial and temporal scales. In the Moroccan ecosystems, small pelagic fish are dominant in biomass, mainly sardine, anchovy and chub mackerel species, whose population dynamics are often associated to the very high physical variability of upwelling. Therefore, this study focuses on the stock assessment of these three species in the Moroccan and Mauritanian waters.

Table 1. Small pelagic fisheries in Morocco and Mauritania (Jeyid, 2016; Pauly et al., 2020; FAO, 2018).

Family/order	Common name	species name (scientific name)
Clupeidae	Herrings	<i>Clupea herrings</i>
	Mehadens	<i>Brevoortia patronus</i>
	Sardine	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>
	Round sardinella	<i>Sardinella aurita</i>
	Sardinella plate	<i>Sardinella maderensis</i>
	Bonga	<i>Ethmalosa fimbriat</i>
Clupeiformes	Shads	<i>Alosa sapidissima</i>
Engraulidae	Anchovies
	european anchovy	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>
	Round herrings	<i>Etrumeus whiteheadi</i>
Inermiidae	Bonnetmouths	<i>Emmelichthyops atlanticus</i>
Myctophidae	Lanternfishes	<i>Myctophum punctatum</i>
Carangidae	Chinchard jaune	<i>Carancho ronchus</i>
	Cunene horse mackerel	<i>Trachurus trecae</i>
	jack mackerel	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>
	False scad	<i>Caranx rhonchus</i>
Scombridae	Atlantic chub mackerel	<i>Scomber colias</i>
Trichiuridae	Silver scabbardfish	<i>Lepidopus caudatus</i>

2.2 Catch data

In the Northwest Africa zones, the decreasing trend in total catch observed from 2010 to 2013 was reversed in 2014. A slight decrease in total catch of the main small pelagic fish in the subregion was observed from 2014 to 2015, from around 2.5 million tonnes in 2014 to around 2.4 million tonnes in 2015, constituting a 5% decrease as compared to 2014. In 2016, an increase of 13% in relation to 2015 was observed. Total catch of small pelagic fish for the period 1990-2016 has been fluctuating with an average of around 1.9 million tonnes while the average for the five last years was 2.4 million tonnes.

More than one million tons of small pelagic are fished annually in recent years by three main fleets: coastal purse seiners, pelagic trawlers equipped with Refrigerated Sea Water (RSW) systems and pelagic freezer trawlers, in addition to an artisanal fishing fleet which has been developing in recent years. In 2017, 1.46 million tonnes of small pelagics were landed. The catches are composed mainly of sardines (73%), chub mackerel (17%) and horse mackerel (7%), Sardinella and anchovy represented only 2% and 1% respectively. This catch is mainly carried out by coastal purse seiners (47%) and RSW trawlers (29%). In spatial terms, most of the catch was made in the southern zone (57%) and the central zone (36%). A summary of the available time series of landings data for the three species is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Available small pelagic (sardine, anchovy and chub mackerel) catches data in Morocco.

Catch data for	Source	zone	period	Fleets and gears type
Sardine	FAO, 2018	All Atlantic Moroccan zones (North+A+B+C zones)	1990-2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moroccan coastal purse-seiners and RSW; • Spanish purse-seiners; • Ukrainian and other pelagic trawlers; • Russian pelagic trawlers; • European Union; • Senegalese fleets.
	CECAF, 2016	<i>Moroccan coast, Sahara coast</i>	1970-2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COPACE captures fleets countries: Morocco, Allemande, Belize, Bulgaria, China, Cyprus, Comoros, Cuba, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, France, Russia, Georgia, Ireland, Lithuania, Mauritania, Norway, Panama, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, United Kingdom, Korea, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Ukraine, Vanuatu.
	Pauly et al., 2020	<i>Moroccan center and south</i>	1950-2014	Moroccan, French and Spanish fleets.
Chub mackerel	FAO, 2018	<i>All Moroccan zones (North+A+B+C zone)</i>	1990-2017	Moroccan, Russian, Ukraine and others, UE fleets
	CECAF, 2016	<i>Moroccan coast, Sahara coast</i>	1970-2018	COPACE captures fleets countries: Morocco, Allemande, Belize, Bulgaria, China, Cyprus, Comoros, Cuba, Denmark, Spain, Estonia, France, Russia, Georgia, Ireland, Japan, Lithuania, Mauritania, Norway, Panama, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, United Kingdom, Korea, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Ukraine, Vanuatu.
	Pauly et al., 2020	<i>Moroccan center and south</i>	1950-2014	Moroccan purse seiners
Anchovy	FAO, 2018	<i>All Moroccan zones (North+A+B+C)</i>	1990-2017	Moroccan, Spanish Russian, Ukrainian and others, European union fleets.
	CECAF, 2016	<i>Moroccan coast, Sahara coast</i>	1970-2018	COPACE captures fleets countries: Morocco, Allemande, Belize, Bulgaria, China, Cyprus, Comoros, Cuba, Spain, France, Russia, Georgia, Ireland, Lithuania, Mauritania, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, United Kingdom, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Ukraine, Vanuatu.
	Pauly et al., 2020	<i>Moroccan center and south</i>	1950-2014	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spain purse seiners • Moroccan purse seiners • Moroccan scale seiners nets • Moroccan encircling nets • Moroccan subsistence fishing gear.

2.2.1 Sardine

Sardine (*S. pilchardus*) remains the dominant small pelagic species, constituting about 73% of the total catch of small pelagic fish in 2017. Catches of this species have fluctuated over the time series, with an average catch of around 728 000 tonnes (1990-2017), and a general increasing trend since 2011. The average catches of sardine over the last five years (2013-2017) were about 898 000 tonnes. The increase is mainly due to an increased availability of the species in Zones A+B (FAO, 2018).

Figure 2. Evolution of Moroccan sardine catches based on different sources of data (FAO, 2016; CECAF, 2016; SAU, Pauly et al., 2020).

2.2.2 Chub mackerel

Chub mackerel (*S. colias*) constitutes around 17% of total small pelagic fish for Morocco in 2017. Catches of this species have also fluctuated over the time period in general, with a general increasing trend since 2012. Total catches in 2017 were about 240 000 tonnes, down from 298 000 tonnes in 2016. Average catch of this species in the last five years is 250 000 tonnes as compared to 134 000 tonnes for the time period 1990-2017 (FAO, 2018).

Chub mackerel catches in Morocco

Figure 3. Evolution of Moroccan chub mackerel catches based on different sources of data (FAO, 2016; CECAF, 2016; Pauly et al., 2020).

2.2.3 Anchovy

The catch of anchovy (*E. encrasicolus*) has shown a general increasing trend from 2004 to 2012, the catches in 2012 were 52 000 tonnes. Catches have decreased since then, with 27 000 tonnes in 2016 to 18 000 tonnes in 2017, a decrease of 31%. The average catch over the last five years is 24 000 tonnes as compared to the long-term average of 22 000 tonnes (FAO, 2018).

Anchovy catches in Morocco

Figure 4. Evolution of Moroccan anchovy catches based on different sources of data (FAO, 2016; CECAF, 2016; Pauly et al., 2020).

2.3 Fishing effort data

The available data on effort by country and by fleet in the Moroccan small pelagic figures are given in table 3.

Table 3: Available fishing effort of the Moroccan small pelagic species (for just sardine and chub mackerel).

Small pelagic species	source	Zone	period	fleets	Fishing effort units
Sardine	FAO, 2018	All Moroccan coast (North+A+B+C zones)	1990-2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moroccan coastal purse seiners • Spanish purse seiners • Moroccan purse seiners RSW • Ukrainian and other pelagic trawlers • Russian Federation • European Union • Others Mauritania • Senegal (artisanal) • Senegal (Industrial) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Trips with sardine catches ➤ Fishing days ➤ Fishing days ➤ Fishing days ➤ Fishing days ➤ Do not target sardine
Chub mackerel	FAO, 2018	North and south of Morocco	1992-2015	Russian federation and Ukraine	Fishing days RTMS
		A+B+C Moroccan zones	1992-2016	Moroccan purse seiners	Number of positive trips

In Morocco, the fishing effort of Spanish coastal purse seiners directed at sardine decreased by 46% in 2016 in terms of the fishing trips in the northern zone compared with 2015, from 599 trips to 323 trips. Likewise, the fishing effort in terms of positive trips with catches of small pelagic fish by Moroccan coastal purse seiners operating in the three fishing zones: north, A and B, declined in 2016 compared to 2015, representing a drop of 47% (from around 15 800 trips to less than 8 500 trips), 26% (from over 11 300 trips to below 8 400) and 11% (from nearly 26 600 trips to less than 23 700 trips) respectively (FAO, 2018).

In Zone C, sardine is fished by a Moroccan national fleet composed of traditional coastal purse seiners and pelagic trawlers equipped with refrigerated sea water (RSW) tanks and by a foreign fleet composed of pelagic freezer trawlers operating under Morocco-Russia and Morocco-EU fishing agreements. The effort by the Moroccan coastal purse seiners decreased in 2016 by 18% compared with 2015, from over 10 200 trips to less than 8 400 trips. The effort reported for the RSW trawlers decreased minimally by 1%, from around 2 750 fishing days in 2015 to almost 2 780 fishing days in 2016 (INRH, 2017). The effort by the Russian pelagic freezer trawlers decreased by 4% in 2016 compared to 2015, from 1 236 fishing days to 1 190 fishing days. The European fleet registered a fishing effort of 627 fishing days in 2016.

2.4 Indices of abundance

The available time series of indices of abundance are given in table 4. The annual abundance index expressed by catch per unit of effort (CPUE) was calculated separately for each sardine and chub mackerel fleet (INRH, 2017). The three different abundance indices, for Zone A+B, the Moroccan and Spanish CPUE and biomass index of R/V Dr. Fridtjof Nansen fleet do not show the same trend (FAO, 2018).

As for Zone C, the CPUE of the pelagic trawler fleet was calculated using the standardised fishing effort for the series 1983-1995, which was used by the last Working Group (FAO, 1997). For the Spanish fleet, the CPUE was calculated for the years 1983-1999; the fishing effort used is expressed in terms of fishing days. Again, different trends can be observed for Spanish and Russian CPUE and the R/V Dr. Fridtjof Nansen biomass index.

Table 4. Available time series of indices of abundance for the three small pelagic target species in Morocco.

CPUE data					
Small pelagic species	Data source	Zone	Period	Fleets	Unit of data
Sardine	FAO, 2018	North+A+B Moroccan zones	1983-2016	Moroccan purse seiners	Moroccan tonnes/positive trips
		Moroccan north zone	2007-2016	Spanish purse seiners	Tonnes/fishing days
		Moroccan C zone	2004-2011 2013-2017	Russian pelagic trawlers	
			2007-2009	Ukraine and other pelagic trawlers	
Chub mackerel	FAO, 2018	A+B+C Moroccan zones	1992-2017	Russian federation and Ukraine	Tonnes/fishing days
		A+B Moroccan zones	1992-2017	Moroccan purse seiners	Tonnes/positive trips
The acoustic biomass indices					
Small pelagic species	Source data	Acoustic surveys	Zone	Period	
Sardine	FAO, 2018	The RV Al Amir Moulay Abdellah	The Moroccan center and south zones	2007-2010	
		F.Nansen		1995-2006	
		R/V Atlantniro	The Moroccan south	1995-2000	
Chub mackerel	FAO, 2018	F.Nansen	The Moroccan south	1999-2015	
		The RV Al Amir Moulay Abdellah	The Moroccan center and south zones	2006-2017	
		The R/V Atlantida	The Moroccan center and south zones	1994-2015	
Anchovy	FAO, 2018	The RV Al Amir Moulay Abdellah	The Moroccan center and south zones	2003-2017	
		The R/V Atlantida	The Moroccan A+B+C zones	1995-2015	

2.4.1 Sardine

The CPUEs of sardine provided by Spanish purse seiners in the Northern zone of Morocco registered the highest levels of the time series available in 2015-2016. The CPUEs for Zones A+B show fluctuations from one year to the next. The CPUEs have fluctuated around an average of 20 tonnes/trip since 2000, with a declining trend from 2003 to 2007, followed by an increase of 20 tonnes/trip in 2009. From 2010, the CPUEs declined over the period 2010-2014 by an average of 17 tonnes per trip. In 2015, CPUEs of 10 tonnes/trip were recorded, the lowest of the series, followed by a small increase in 2016 to 12 tonnes/trip. In Zone C north of Cape Blanc, the CPUEs of sardine from the Russian fleet dropped from 21 tonnes/fishing day in 2015 to 18 tonnes/fishing day in 2016, although it should be noted that the effort of the Russian fleet is not directed at sardine (FAO, 2018).

2.4.2 Chub mackerel

The CPUEs of purse seiners in the northern fishery show a large increase from 2002 to 2007, when a peak of 2.77 tonnes/trip was observed. Since then, the CPUEs suffered a decline which worsened in 2012 (1.26 tonnes/trip in 2011 and 1.08 tonnes/trip in 2012) and this was maintained until 2014 despite a slight recovery of the CPUEs in 2013 (1.3 tonnes/trip). Between 2014 and 2016, the annual CPUEs of the Moroccan purse seiners in the northern fishery increased sharply to 1.52 tonnes/trip in 2015 and 2.5 tonnes/trip in 2016. The standardized CPUE of the Russian fleet in tonnes/day by fishing freezer trawlers (RTMS) shows a general downward trend during the period with fluctuations. In 2010 and 2011, the CPUEs were maintained around 42 tonnes/day RTMS. In 2013, the standardized CPUE of the Russian fleet fell sharply to 35 tonnes/day and increased in 2014 to exceed the level of 42 tonnes/day RTMS. In 2015, the standardized CPUE declined by 14% compared with 2014 to 37 tonnes/day RTMS and then stabilized around the same value in 2016. An analysis of the trend of yields of chub mackerel from the Moroccan purse seiners operating in the Zones A+B and the standardized CPUE of the Russian fleet indicates opposing directions and thus shows different trends between the two indices. In 2016, this difference could be the result of the strong presence of the new generation 0+ of which 90% are found in Zones A+B outside the fishing zones exploited by Russian trawlers (FAO, 2018).

2.4.3 Anchovy

In the absence of data on fishing effort targeting anchovy, the available CPUEs cannot be considered as reliable indices of relative abundance. The estimated CPUEs for Spanish purse seiners in the northern zone of Morocco are around 900-1 000 kg/ fishing day over the last two years. These CPUEs are much lower than those obtained during the period 2007-2011, which reached a maximum of 2 321 kg / fishing day in 2011 (FAO, 2012).

2.5 Length composition data

The available data on length distributions of the three small pelagic species is given in table 5.

Table 5. Available length composition data for the three small pelagic target species in Morocco.

Length composition				
Small pelagic species	Data sources	Zone	Period	Fleets
Sardine	FAO, 2018	All Moroccan coast (the north+A+B+C)	2006-2017	AtlantNiro (Kaliningrad)
Chub mackerel		The Moroccan north zone	2009-2017	The RV Al Amir Moulay Abdellah
		The Moroccan south zone	2011-2017	The RV Al Amir Moulay Abdellah and the R/V Atlantida
Anchovy		Moroccan A+B+North zones	2014-2017	R /V Al-Amir Moulay Abdellah
Age composition				
Sardine	FAO, 2018	The Moroccan center and south (A+B+C zones)	1990-2017	R /V Al-Amir Moulay Abdellah
Chub mackerel		The northern and southern Moroccan fisheries	1992-2017	From Russian Federation
Mean weight at age				
Sardine	FAO, 2018	The Moroccan center and south coast (A+B+C zones)	1990-2017	R /V Al-Amir Moulay Abdellah
Mean length at age				
Sardine	INRH, 2018	The Moroccan center coast (A+B zones)	2003-2017	R /V Al-Amir Moulay Abdellah
	Russian samples	The Moroccan south coast (C zone)	2003-2017	the R/V Atlantida

2.5.1 Sardine stock

The length distribution of sardine in 2014, based on the biological sampling of Moroccan and Spanish landings of vessels operating in the northern Moroccan zone, is bi-modal with a main mode at 19 cm and a secondary mode at 14 cm. Those corresponding to landings of Moroccan vessels operating in the central zone (A+B) is tri-modal with a main mode at 16.5 cm and two secondary modes at 20 cm and 23 cm (FAO, 2012). In the southern zone of Cape Bojador, the dominant mode of the length distribution of sardine in 2016 was 24 cm (FAO,2017). The length distribution of sardine in Zone C was estimated on the basis of Moroccan and Russian catch data for the zone Cape Bojador-Cape Blanc and on the basis of Russian and European catch data for the zone south of Cape Blanc. The age/length key for sardine in Zones A+B was established by INRH scientists for 2016. For Zone C, the age/length keys of Russian samples used for 2016 were established by Russian scientists in the zones north and south of Cape Blanc.

Sardine age compositions and average weights by age were updated for 2016 in Zones A+B and for Zone C. The average lengths by age show differences in growth rate from one age to the next. The

length/weight coefficients used were estimated using data from the sampling carried out in Moroccan ports in 2016, while the growth parameters were determined by Length Frequency Distribution Analysis (LFDA) on the 2016 length distribution series for sardine in Zones A+B and Zone C.

2.5.2 Chub mackerel

The length composition of mackerel catches in Zones North (between Cape Spartel and Cape Cantin) and A+B was based on Moroccan data. In Zone C, the length composition was based on Moroccan and Russian data (Morocco and Mauritania) as well as Senegalese data (FAO, 2001). The length frequency distribution for mackerel was analysed for Zones North, A+B and South and compared to that of previous years. The length frequency distributions from the Moroccan purse seiners landings in Zones A+B in 2006 had a bimodal distribution with a main mode of young individuals at 12 cm and a secondary mode at 22 cm. Between 2007 and 2010, the length distribution was unimodal with a mode at 20 cm in 2007, 19 cm in 2008, 21 cm in 2009 and 21 cm in 2010. In the following years, the length distribution was bimodal with non-pronounced modes at 16 cm and 21 cm in 2011, 17 and 18 cm in 2012, 11 and 19 cm in 2013 and 17 and 20 cm in 2014. In 2015, the length distribution of mackerel in this zone had two modes; a main mode at 19 cm and a secondary mode at 16 cm. The length distribution was the same in 2016 with two modes: a main mode at 14 cm and a secondary mode at 20 cm. Besides, an analysis of the average length of mackerel in Zones A+B shows an increasing trend over the last three years unlike the period 2010-2013 that was marked by a decline in the average length. This average length was around 19 cm between 2015 and 2016. In the zone south of Cape Bojador, the length distribution of landings in 2006 was characterized by a main mode of 23 cm and also the presence of lengths reaching 46 cm. In 2007, three main modes were observed at 20, 24 and 30 cm (FAO, 2018).

As in previous years, the age-length key for mackerel was obtained from the distribution of Russian commercial samples in 2016 into age groups. This key was then used to estimate the total and average weight by age for chub mackerel landed in the whole sub-region. The estimated age compositions and average weights by age in the northern and southern regions and for the whole sub-region have been updated. Overall, the average weights by age groups estimated for all ages in 2014 and 2015 are identical, with some minor differences for ages 6+ (INRH, 2017).

2.5.3 Anchovy

The length distribution of anchovy catches of the Spanish purse seiners operating in the north of Morocco in 2016 range between 10 cm and 17 cm, with two modes at 11 cm and 15.5 cm. The smaller individuals (11 cm) were caught mainly during the first quarter, while the large individuals were caught during the second quarter (average size = 14.4 cm). However, there was no fishing during the fourth quarter (FAO, 2017).

2.6 Life history parameters

The life history parameters for the three target species were obtained from data from multiple sources: the acoustic survey campaigns (aboard the N/R. Al Amir Moulay Abdellah), the national sampling program (biological parameters for commercial catches), and the survey program carried out by central and regional laboratories. The available growth, and weight-length relationship, natural mortality and length at first maturity parameters for the three small pelagic species is summarised in table 6.

Table 6. Age and growth parameters, weight-length relationship, natural mortality and length at first maturity parameters of the three small pelagic target species in Morocco (INRH, 2017).

Moroccan stocks	Growth parameters			Weight-length parameters			Natural mortality M (1/year)	Length at first maturity L50 (cm)
	L_{∞} (cm)	K (yr ⁻¹)	t0 (yr)	a	b	r ²		
Sardine								
A+B Stock	29.32	0.590	-0.570	0.0089	2.964	0.96	1,35	14.83
C Stock	27.9	0.53	-0.6	0.0094	2.987	0.90		18.48
Chub mackerel								
A+B Stock	35.78	0.27	-0.78	0.0077	3.0205	0.89	0.60	22.56
C stock	45.06	0.29	-0.75	0.007	3.05	0.92		24.24
Anchovy								
A+°B Stock	17	1.39	-0.15	0.0041	3.1818	0.9075	0.93	10.05

3 Mauritanian coast

With a coastline of 720 km, an Exclusive Economic Zone extending 230 km from the coast and highly productive waters, fishing is one of the most important economic sectors in Mauritania (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Mauritanian Atlantic coast and EEZ (FAO, 2001).

3.1 Catch data

The available time series of catches of small pelagic species in Mauritanian waters is given in table 7. Catches of all the main small pelagic fish in Mauritania have shown interannual fluctuations over the period from 1990 to 2017 with an overall increasing trend from 1994 until 2010, followed by a general decreasing trend from 2010 until 2013. In 2010, the total catches of the main small pelagic fish were the highest of the time series (1 186 000 tonnes) before decreasing again until 2013 (536 000 tonnes). In 2014, the catches increased again and reached 794 000 tonnes, in 2015 the total catch fell down 23% with 614 000 tonnes. In 2016, catches increased again 38% in relation to 2015 with a catch of about 848 000 tonnes (FAO, 2017).

Table 7. Available time series of small pelagic catch data from Mauritania.

Small pelagic species	Data Source	zone	period	Fleets type
Sardine	FAO, 2018	Mauritanian coast	1990-2017	Mauritanian artisanal fleets
	CECAF, 2016	Mauritanian coast	1970-2016	Countries with vessels in COPACE area: Belize, Bulgaria, China, Cyprus, Comoros, Cuba, Germany, Spain, France, Russia, Georgia, Ireland, Lithuania, Mauritania, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Norway, United Kingdom, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Ukraine, Vanuatu
	Fishbase, 2018		1950-2017	Mauritanian artisanal fleets
	SAU, 2016		1950-2014	Mauritanian fleets (artisanal, industrial and subsistence)
Chub mackerel	FAO, 2018	Mauritanian coast	1990-2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU-type (Lithuania) • EU-type (Holland) • Non-EU • Artisanal
	CECAF, 2016		1990-2016	Russian fleets
	SAU, 2016		1950-2014	Mauritanian artisanal fleets
Anchovy	FAO, 2018	Mauritanian coast	1990-2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Russian, Ukraine and others • Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia and Poland
	CECAF, 2016		1970-2016	Countries with vessels in COPACE area: Germany, Belize, Bulgaria, China, Cyprus, Comoros, Cuba, Spain, France, Russia, Georgia, Ireland, Lithuania, Mauritania, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, United Kingdom, Saint Kitts and Nevis, Ukraine, Vanuatu.
	SAU, 2016		1950-2014	Mauritanian fleets (artisanal and industrial)
	Fishbase, 2018		1950-2017	Mauritanian artisanal fleets

3.1.1 Sardine

Sardine (*S. pilchardus*) remained the dominant small pelagic species catches in the catches in Mauritania in 2017, constituting 21%, 19%, 15%, and 20% respectively of the total catch of small pelagic. The total catch of this species increased from 79 000 tonnes in 2016 to 166 000 tonnes in 2017s (FAO, 2018).

Sardine catches in Mauritania

Figure 6. Evolution of sardine catches in Mauritania, based on four sources. (FAO, 2016; CECAF, 2016; Pauly et al., 2020; Fishbase, 2018).

3.1.2 Chub mackerel

Catches of chub mackerel (*S. colias*) also almost doubled in 2014, from about 42 000 in 2013 to 83 000 tonnes in 2014 (FAO, 2012). Catches doubled again from 2016 to 2017 (82 000 tonnes to 123 000 tonnes, respectively), a 51% increase. Three sources of catch data are available: FAO: all fleets and zones, CECAF: for Mauritanian fleets, and Sea around us (SAU), for all fleets and zones (Figure 7).

Chub mackerel catches in Mauritania

Figure 7. Evolution of chub mackerel catches in Mauritania, based on three sources. (FAO, 2016; CECAF, 2016; Pauly et al., 2020)

3.1.3 Anchovy

Anchovy catches of Anchovy (*E. encrasicolus*) shows large fluctuations over the time series. In 2014, catches of this species were 1 400 tonnes, decreasing from 3 000 tonnes in 2013, decreasing again in 2015 and 2016, only to increase 8% to 1492 tonnes in 2017 (FAO, 2018).

Figure 8. Evolution of anchovy catches in Mauritania, based on four sources (FAO, 2016; CECAF, 2016; Pauly et al., 2020; Fishbase, 2018).

3.2 Fishing effort data

In the Mauritanian zone, the effort by the Mauritanian coastal purse seiners in 2016 was 1 859 trips while that of the Russian fleet and others was 6 779 fishing days. The European fleet recorded an effort of 1 341 fishing days (FAO, 2017).

In 2016, there was an increase in fishing effort in the Mauritanian zone after the return of the EU fleet. The fishing effort series for all fleets operating in the Mauritanian coast were not compiled. No review of effort data (corrections, missing series, etc.) was done in the region (FAO, 2018).

4 Environmental data

Recruitment of small pelagic species could be modulated by different environmental factors, including abiotic (e.g., sea temperature or sea salinity) and biotic (e.g., food abundance). However, long-term measurements of environmental conditions are rare and scattered so we need to resort to numerical models in order to obtain comprehensive datasets that could be compared with the fisheries data described above.

One major data source on marine environmental data is the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) portal (<https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/>) where different databases, including modelling products can be accessed. Those databases have been trimmed based on spatial and temporal coverage, available variables and spatial and temporal resolution in order to find the most suitable ones to extract the environmental information needed to feed into the stock models.

For abiotic parameters (e.g., sea temperature and salinity), the Global Ocean Physical Reanalysis (product id: GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030) has been selected. This product is the CMEMS global ocean eddy-resolving ($1/12^\circ$ horizontal resolution and 50 vertical levels) reanalysis covering the altimetry era 1993-2018. It is based largely on the current real-time global forecasting CMEMS system. The model component is the NEMO platform driven at the surface by ECMWF ERA-Interim reanalysis. Observations are assimilated by means of a reduced-order Kalman filter. Along track altimeter data (Sea Level Anomaly), satellite Sea Surface Temperature, Sea Ice Concentration and in situ temperature and salinity vertical profiles are jointly assimilated. Moreover, a 3D-VAR scheme provides a correction for the slowly-evolving large-scale biases in temperature and salinity. This product includes daily and monthly mean files of the selected variables from the top to the bottom.

For biotic parameters (e.g., chlorophyll or primary production rate), the corresponding product is the Global Ocean Biogeochemistry Hindcast (product id: GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_BIO_001_029). It provides 3D biogeochemical fields for the time period 1993-2019 at $1/4$ degree and on 75 vertical levels and it uses PISCES biogeochemical model. The spatial resolution of this model is 3 times coarser than the physical component, which could impact on the quality of the simulated variables. CMEMS provides another biogeochemical dataset (product id: IBI_REANALYSIS_BIO_005_003) with the higher $1/12^\circ$ resolution but that only includes up to 26° north (i.e., leaving out Zone C from Morocco and the entire Mauritania fishing grounds). We plan to use both, the coarser and the finer resolution products for the northernmost fishing grounds in Morocco in order to evaluate if there are significant differences in the environmental conditions from both datasets and if that could be related to population trends estimated by stock-assessment models.

All environmental datasets cover the period 1993 to 2018 and provide both daily and monthly fields. From the original 3D fields provided by the models, average daily and monthly values over each of the fishing regions are computed so the environmental variability during the common duration of both time-series (fishing and environment) could be analysed and included in the developed models.

5 Discussion/ Conclusion

This report shows how progress has been made within the FarFish project, with regard to data compilation for small pelagics in the West coast of Africa. Most of the data were found in FAO/CECAF and regional reports. The project does still not have direct access to the data from EAF-Nansen programme surveys, but some acoustic biomass indices from this programme were found in these reports for Sardine and Chub mackerel in the Moroccan Southern zone.

The data compiled for the Moroccan coast can be used as input for Surplus production models and also length or age-based models. Nevertheless, some difficulty is envisaged for using the Mauritanian data into some models that could provide estimated population trends because data is very limited in this case.

In the WP6, framework abundance indexes will be filtered to select harvestable biomass by using the length and age distributions and then used with catches time series to fit Surplus production models in Continuous time (SPiCT, Pedersen et al. 2016, Mildenberger et al. 2019). These models will provide reference points, estimated biomass and fishing mortality trends that could be used to find mathematical relationships with environmental variables, as illustrated in Rincon et al. (2019), where Granger causality were found to link recruitment estimates and strong winds for anchovy in the Gulf of Cadiz. In addition, Many studies have identified possible assumptions that link environmental effects to changes in stock abundance (Jeyid, 2016). As result of their biological characteristics, high mobility and ability as fast swimmers, small pelagic species are typically very sensitive to environmental forcing (Cury & Roy, 1989; FAO, 2016). So it should be necessary to include environmental variability in fisheries management approaches (Hofmann & Powell, 1998). In the north-west of Africa, the effect of environmental variations on the distribution and abundance of chub mackerel is an important issue that continues challenging scientists and fishery managers. The main limitation on determining the relationships between the environment and population dynamics is the short data sets that are generally available (Baali et al., 2019; Belvèze, 1991).

In summary, data compiled provides enough information to fulfil the model requirements for the Moroccan area and also it describes the sources for different environmental variables as the first step to explore the relationship between the population dynamics and the environment. The advantage of this approach is that it would assess population status and at the same time it would contribute to disentangle the environmental effect over the pelagic ecosystem.

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